

Measurement Science and Technology

PERSPECTIVE

OPEN ACCESS

RECEIVED
30 October 2025

REVISED
11 February 2026

ACCEPTED FOR PUBLICATION
26 March 2026

PUBLISHED
15 April 2026

Original content from this work may be used under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 licence](#).

Any further distribution of this work must maintain attribution to the author(s) and the title of the work, journal citation and DOI.

Recent advances and perspectives in quantum electrical metrology with epitaxial graphene

Dong-Hun Chae^{1,*}

¹ Korea Research Institute of Standards and Science (KRISS), Daejeon 34113, Republic of Korea

² RISE Research Institutes of Sweden, Box 857, S-50115 Borås, Sweden

³ Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB), Bundesallee 100, 38116 Braunschweig, Germany

* Author to whom any correspondence should be addressed.

E-mail: dhchae@kriss.re.kr

Keywords: epitaxial graphene, quantum Hall effect, quantum electrical metrology

Abstract

Quantum electrical metrology is an important application of collective states of matter. One prominent example is the quantum Hall condensate, which is essential for the realization of the resistance unit, the ohm. In graphene, the linear energy-momentum dispersion of quasiparticles allows for a practical realization of the quantum Hall resistance standard under easily accessible experimental conditions of temperature and magnetic field. With the maturity of technology, epitaxial graphene devices are now gradually deployed for primary resistance quantum standards at national metrology institutes. Here, we present the latest advances and future perspectives of graphene-based quantum electrical metrology, highlighting how this material can not only improve the realization conditions for the quantum resistance standard but also extend quantum-accurate realization of the ohm for the betterment of impedance and current metrology.

1. Introduction

Graphene is two-dimensional graphite, consisting of a single layer of carbon atoms arranged in a hexagonal lattice. It is a semimetal with the valence and conduction bands touching at zero energy in the band structure. Near these touching points (Dirac points), the energy-momentum dispersion relation is linear, so charged quasiparticles in graphene consequently behave as massless fermions with a Fermi velocity of $1 \times 10^6 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ (much less than c) [1]. This linear dispersion underpins graphene's distinctive physics.

More than two decades ago, the Manchester group led by A. Geim isolated graphene from graphite on an oxidized silicon substrate using adhesive tape [2]. Similar exfoliation techniques had been used previously to peel thin layers from graphite [3, 4], and surface scientists had also investigated synthetic graphene on metals [5, 6] and insulating carbides [7, 8]. Unlike earlier studies, the Manchester group and the Harvard group led by P. Kim fabricated graphene devices and simultaneously reported observations of the characteristic half-integer quantum Hall effect (QHE) at low temperatures [9, 10]. This measurement triggered a surge of research on graphene in the scientific community. The Nobel Prize in Physics 2010 was then awarded jointly to A. Geim and K. Novoselov 'for groundbreaking experiments regarding the two-dimensional material graphene' [11]. Compared with the Landau-level spacing in two-dimensional electrons with finite effective masses at the interfaces of semiconducting heterostructures, the linear dispersion relation in graphene leads to an unusually large energy separation between the zeroth and first Landau levels, supporting a robust quantum Hall state at filling factor 2 [9, 10]. The corresponding energy spacing under a magnetic field of 1 T is approximately 50 meV, roughly twice the thermal energy at room temperature. This allows the QHE to emerge in graphene even at room temperature under an accessible high magnetic field [12]. This implies that the QHE can be realized in graphene at relatively higher temperatures and lower magnetic fields, which is important in quantum electrical metrology from a practical perspective.

There are various forms of graphene. Since the successful isolation of graphene in Manchester, exfoliated graphene flakes have been an impetus for scientific studies in laboratories. This type of graphene, however, is not suitable for practical applications owing to its limited size and irregular shape. Scalable graphene can be synthesized through chemical vapor deposition (CVD) on metals such as copper [13] or nickel [6]. CVD graphene must be transferred to a target substrate. However, the transfer process induces tears, wrinkles, and folds in the thin atomic layer. Alternatively, graphene can be obtained by graphitizing silicon carbide (SiC) [7]. Controlled sublimation of silicon atoms above 1500 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ leads to graphene growth from the remaining carbon atoms on the silicon-terminated face [14, 15]. This material is commonly called ‘epitaxial graphene’ even though it is not grown epitaxially using molecular-beam epitaxy. Because SiC is a wide-bandgap insulator, especially at cryogenic temperatures, graphene devices can be microfabricated directly on the growth SiC substrate without transfer. In addition, effective heat conduction from the graphene device to the SiC substrate is expected owing to SiC’s high thermal conductivity, which is advantageous for electronic devices.

The discovery of the QHE [16] by K. von Klitzing played a key role in establishing quantum electrical metrology, together with the Josephson effect [17]. That is, quantum resistance and voltage standards are realized by the QHE and the Josephson effect, respectively. These are good examples of how measurements have enabled discoveries and, reciprocally, have been enabled by them. The robust QHE in graphene has attracted the attention of electrical metrologists. The metrology community has focused on epitaxial graphene as a scalable platform to develop a practically accessible quantum resistance standard for more than a decade and a half. Since epitaxial graphene is highly electron-doped owing to charge transfer from SiC [18], hole doping is generally required to achieve quantization at practical temperatures and magnetic fields.

The degree of equivalence between quantum Hall resistances (QHRs) in epitaxial graphene and in conventional gallium arsenide (GaAs) heterostructure has been demonstrated within 0.1 $\text{n}\Omega/\Omega$ [19]. Contrary to expectations, the required magnetic fields and temperatures for metrological Hall quantization in early epitaxial graphene devices were almost equivalent to those in conventional GaAs devices [19, 20], likely due to disorder, high electron doping in as-grown epitaxial graphene, or overlayer molecules for hole doping. Through optimization of the device-fabrication process and hole doping, the quantum resistance standard has been realized under practical conditions at a magnetic field of ~ 5 T and a temperature of ~ 4 K [21, 22]. Note that this condition can be achieved cost-effectively in a relatively compact closed-cycle cryomagnet, unlike the counterparts ($B \sim 10$ T and $T \leq 2$ K) for GaAs devices, which have been the basis for three decades in the ohm realization, in typical wet cryostats. Graphene devices are a pragmatic alternative to GaAs for the use as quantum resistance standards, owing to more practical operation conditions, as shown in figure 1.

Epitaxial graphene is already in use in national metrology institutes (NMIs) to advance beyond the current state of the art in quantum electrical metrology. Since reliable QHR realization at direct current (DC) has become possible, its metrological applications have extended. For impedance quantum standards, the wide, flat Hall plateau quantization above a threshold magnetic field has been realized at alternating current (AC) below frequencies of a few kHz [28]. GaAs however exhibits a narrow and barely flat plateau owing to the intrinsic parasitic capacitance at the interface. The capacitance has been compared with graphene-based QHR at AC to achieve direct traceability to the elementary charge of e and the Planck constant of h in the International System of Units (SI) [29]. Integration of graphene Hall devices has extended the range of QHR at the fixed value of $h/(2e^2)$ near $12.9\text{ k}\Omega$ from $100\ \Omega$ to $10\text{ M}\Omega$ [30–33]. It also enables extension of the electrical current range at metrology-grade levels. For instance, an integrated parallel graphene array has been employed to generate a precise current at mA level for the kilogram realization with a Kibble balance at the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) [34]. As outlined above, epitaxial graphene is now deployed for quantum electrical metrology in NMIs, whereas other industrial applications [35, 36] of graphene, including electronics, flexible interconnections, photodetectors, and bio-sensors, remain under development.

In this Perspective, we describe recent advances in quantum electrical metrology, enabled by epitaxial graphene, and provide perspectives on each area. Section 2 describes advancements in device fabrication, followed by developments for the long-term stability of epitaxial graphene devices in section 3. Recent verifications of the reliability of graphene-based quantum resistance standards are presented in section 4. Progress on graphene-based impedance quantum standards is described in section 5. Section 6 provides late developments in electrical current metrology. The conclusion and outlook follow in section 7.

2. Fabrication of epitaxial graphene devices

The primary application for graphene in metrology is as a quantum resistance standard, which relies on the QHE where a high degree of accuracy is essential [26]. This imposes stringent requirements on both the quality of the base graphene material and the fabrication processes used to transform it into a functional device. To unlock the full advantages of graphene, the material must be of high quality, specifically a monolayer of monocrystalline film. The growth of such a material is challenging as it typically requires balancing quality (e.g. exfoliated flakes) and quantity (e.g. CVD). The purity of the material should also ideally be preserved on its journey through various microfabrication process steps.

This section discusses the advancements made in graphene technology which has rapidly transformed the material from its origins in research laboratories into a commercial product used for electrical metrology. It also summarizes the fabrication of epitaxial graphene QHR devices, highlighting the growth methods, contamination control, contact design, carrier-density control, and packaging required to achieve metrological-grade devices.

2.1. Material choice

While the name graphene typically refers to the nanomaterial consisting of a one-atom-thin sheet of carbon atoms, in practice, there exists a host of materials under the umbrella of graphene (see ISO/TS 80 004-13:2017 for a list of the extended family). Even just focusing on high-quality monolayer graphene, the methods by which the material is grown impact its properties and useful applications. For metrological use, the popular candidates are: exfoliated graphene flakes [9], films grown by CVD [13], and epitaxial growth on SiC [14, 37].

The graphene boom started with the Nobel prize-winning method of mechanically exfoliating micrometer-sized flakes of graphene from graphite. While this method can produce high-quality graphene devices, its use is mainly limited to research due to the small device sizes and labor-intensive, non-scalable nature of the manual fabrication process.

Large areas of graphene can be grown on metallic substrates using CVD, enabling orders of magnitude larger films to be rapidly produced [38]. However, the quality is typically not ideal for use in quantum metrology since the large CVD films are polycrystalline and the presence of grain boundaries negatively impacts performance. Using more refined methods, it is possible to grow large, millimeter-scale areas of CVD monolayer monocrystalline graphene [39]. However, one constant problem that remains is that CVD graphene needs to be transferred from the conductive metallic substrates to an insulating substrate for electrical applications. Various transfer methods exist, but they all invariably introduce defects in the film, whether through contamination or mechanical deformation [13]. This limitation restricts the application of CVD graphene for quantum electrical metrology.

Epitaxial growth of graphene on SiC is a method which can produce large-area monolayer monocrystalline graphene by thermal decomposition of the substrate. In short, an insulating SiC substrate is placed in an oven, where silicon sublimates at high temperatures, leaving a carbon layer which eventually forms a graphene layer covering the SiC surface. Graphene is the conductive active layer, with an insulating buffer layer beneath it and both resting on the insulating SiC substrate providing mechanical support (figure 2). This process yields a material that, in principle, is ready for use as an electrical device once removed from the growth oven. Additional microfabrication steps to define the device geometry and to deposit contacts, do not significantly degrade performance if performed carefully.

The substrate exerts some influence on the electrical properties of epitaxial graphene. The high thermal conductivity of SiC and strong coupling to graphene enable high current bias operation, thereby improving signal-to-noise ratio [40, 41]. Additionally, the strong interaction with the substrate and interface buffer layer results in a magnetic field dependent charge transfer [42], greatly extending the width of the quantized resistance plateaus and simplifying the use of graphene in quantum electrical metrology [43]. However, a drawback of the substrate interaction is the strong n-type doping and Fermi level pinning, which complicates the control of graphene's carrier density.

Overall, the pros outweigh the cons, and epitaxial graphene is regarded as ideal for practical metrological applications and is gradually replacing conventional semiconductors as the premier material for quantum resistance metrology.

The technology behind epitaxial graphene is mature enough that the material can be purchased commercially with sufficiently high quality for quantum metrology.

The growth methods are continuously improving, making epitaxial graphene more readily available, with higher quality [44, 45]. The price is also decreasing, although much of the cost is tied to the price of the SiC substrate itself. The improved yield of high-quality graphene over larger areas (wafer-scale growth) is one way to alleviate this issue.

2.2. Growth methods

Growth of monolayer epitaxial graphene commonly occurs on semi-insulating 6 H-SiC(0001) or 4 H-SiC(0001). The fundamental principle involves heating the substrate at high temperatures, causing silicon to sublime and leaving behind a carbon-rich layer which subsequently forms graphene. Key parameters which influence the quality of the final material include temperature (typically between 1750 °C and 1900 °C), time (ramp rates), atmosphere (typically ~1 bar argon atmosphere), partial pressures of silicon and carbon, and more. Numerous variations of this method exist, such as confining the substrate [15], face-to-graphite sublimation [46], and the introduction of additional precursors,

Figure 3. Photograph of a reactor for epitaxial graphene growth.

including polymer-assisted sublimation growth or CVD growth of epitaxial graphene [45, 47]. A suitable growth reactor for epitaxial graphene is shown in figure 3.

A good starting point is to use a low wafer miscut angle (typically 0.1° – 0.2°) and polished substrate. Addition of precursors supplies carbon that facilitates early nucleation of the buffer layer and suppresses step bunching during high-temperature graphitization. When properly controlled, it is possible to consistently yield bilayer-free monolayers over $5 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$ chips with sub-nanometer terrace steps, minimal bilayer patches, and excellent uniformity which are key factors for the fabrication of millimeter-scale Hall bars achieving high breakdown currents [44, 48].

2.3. Quality assurance

Before proceeding with fabrication, the quality of the graphene material should be investigated. It is important to ensure that the material consists of monolayer graphene, without large defects. A common method for this assessment is Raman spectroscopy, which identifies the characteristic fingerprints of monolayer graphene [49]. However, it is important to note that the SiC substrate can complicate the interpretation of the Raman spectra [50].

Alternatively, express optical methods can be used to quickly assess the homogeneity of growth and scan the entire sample for defects such as multilayer graphene, holes (incomplete growth), and contaminants (e.g. dust) [51, 52]. A representative image of epitaxial graphene obtained by optical microscopy is shown in figure 4. Typically for metrological-grade devices, the monolayer coverage should be above 95%, ideally 99% or better to ensure a high device yield.

2.4. Device design and considerations

Numerous different approaches exist to fabricate devices from graphene in general. The devices used for quantum metrology typically employ graphene in defined in a rectangular Hall bar geometry. The Hall bar should have at least six contacts: one pair for current bias, one pair for measuring the transverse Hall voltage and one pair for the longitudinal voltage. The dimensions of the Hall bar, and therefore the distance between contacts, should be sufficiently large to minimize the influence of heating at the current injection points, commonly referred as to the hot spots in the quantum Hall regime [53]. Figure 5 shows a mounted QHR device on a TO-8 chip holder, along with an optical micrograph.

There are many valid approaches to achieve this relatively simple design [20, 21, 24, 44, 48, 54], but the result should always be a device with low charge disorder/high carrier mobility and low contact resistance. The carrier mobility also influences the operation parameters that are required to reach the QHR plateau. Low mobility can be partially mitigated by using higher magnetic fields, lower temperatures, and lower bias currents, but only up to a point before it becomes impractical.

The fabrication methods use either electron beam lithography or photolithography to define the graphene and contact structures. The size of the Hall bar is typically large enough that the difference in resolution is insignificant. The main difference lies in the different chemistries of the resists and developers, many of which will irreversibly alter the properties of graphene and change the carrier density and mobility. The nanoscopic contaminants left on graphene are difficult to remove using just simple

Figure 4. Optical image of epitaxial graphene taken using transmission mode microscopy and enhanced using post-processing. Darker regions indicate the presence of bilayer patches with examples encircled in red. The rest of the light gray area represents monolayer graphene.

Figure 5. (a) Photograph showing a graphene quantum Hall resistance standard chip ($7 \times 7 \text{ mm}^2$) mounted to a sample holder. (b) Optical micrograph of a graphene Hall bar taken using transmission mode microscopy, showing the central graphene channel and three Hall crosses.

solvents [55]. To preserve the quality of graphene one effective approach involves using a metal mask, such as gold, to protect the graphene throughout the process steps. The mask is subsequently removed at the end of the fabrication [48]. This method has been shown to work well for metrological applications.

2.5. Contacts

Poor contacts can both introduce excess noise and induce errors in the accuracy of quantization, and should be well-below 10Ω per contact [26]. Making a good (i.e. ohmic) contact to low-dimensional materials is not trivial [56]. The choice of contact material, geometry, and the condition of the nanomaterial itself all play a role. For graphene, many different ideas have been tested to find a reliable approach [57–59]. Currently the best contacts are one-dimensional edge contacts, but the process relies on encapsulating graphene flakes between hexagonal boron nitride, which is not scalable [60]. Recent advances have shown that there is a way to create pseudo edge contacts using regular lithography, which makes it a scalable approach to low-contact resistances [61]. Another trick to reduce the influence of contact resistance, in the case for measurements of the QHR, is to use multi-terminal leads [33, 59, 62].

For single DC and AC devices, PTB typically uses normal-metal bond pads (Ti/Au) with defined overlaps to the PdAu/Au-covered graphene edges in the contact regions. These contacts (source/drain and potential contacts) are split into multiple branches (figure 6). In the QHE regime the current preferentially enters the first branch near the hot spot. Successive branches carry exponentially less current,

effectively realizing a Delahaye-style multiple-series connection inside a single contact with minimal overall resistance. The branched contact design opened a new route in the development of QHR arrays since, in combination with superconducting materials such as NbTiN or NbN, the two-terminal and four-terminal resistances of devices become equal within measurement uncertainty [31, 33, 59, 63]. In parallel, major developments in the microfabrication of graphene single devices and large arrays were demonstrated by RISE and partners with a scalable edge-contact process that achieves consistently minimal contact resistance and high yield [61].

2.6. Fabrication steps

The standard method at PTB involves early protection of the graphene surface to limit lithography residues. Immediately after growth and chip selection, a thin noble-metal capping stack (PdAu/Au, $\sim 20/40$ nm) is evaporated onto the epitaxial graphene. The Hall bar structure is then defined by optical lithography and sequential wet etching using potassium iodide solution and Ar-plasma reactive ion dry etching, while leaving the active graphene areas capped and thus protected from contamination. After defining bond pads (Ti/Au 10/100 nm), the protective PdAu/Au above graphene is selectively removed by optical lithography and potassium-iodide wet etch to expose a clean epitaxial graphene surface in the Hall bar region. This resist-shielded fabrication sequence reduces polymer residues at the graphene/metal interface and correlates with low contact resistances and robust quantization [48, 64].

Other approaches to device fabrication omit the protective metal mask, in favor of simpler fabrication steps. The main difference is that the metal capping step and metal etching step described above can be skipped. Due to unavoidable resist residuals, it is important that the resists used are compatible with the polymers and chemical dopants used in subsequent encapsulation steps (see below). A common choice is to use mainly polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA)-based resists, which preserves the quality of graphene enough for metrological applications [50, 59].

2.7. Carrier density control

The benefits of epitaxial graphene for electrical metrology are many, but the use of the material does come with its own challenges. One major aspect which needs consideration is the control over the charge carrier density. Since the carrier density level is closely related to the electrical properties of the material, it offers a convenient way to tune the performance of graphene. The carrier density must also satisfy the filling factor of the Landau levels, which is determined by the ratio of the carrier density to the magnetic field, for the emergence of the QHE under a practical magnetic field.

For electrical metrology, the carrier density is important due to its link to carrier mobility. A necessary condition for the existence of the QHE is that the electrons have time to complete their cyclotron orbits due to an external magnetic field. In the end, this condition translates to the necessity for high carrier mobility, which reduces the minimum magnetic field required to observe the QHE, as described by the relation: $B_{\min} \gg 1/\mu$. For the practical application of graphene in metrology, the carrier mobility should therefore be high.

The quality of the material influences carrier mobility since the presence of defects, contaminants and other inhomogeneities will impede the transport of the electrons. Furthermore, a high charge carrier density will also affect the carrier mobility negatively since the existence of many carriers will increase

the likelihood of collisions. Epitaxial graphene is of high quality since it is a monolayer monocrystalline material and generally has low defect density. However, the substrate influences the mobility negatively due to high induced carrier density level and increased scattering caused by substrate dangling bonds [42, 65]. The charge transfer between the substrate and epitaxial graphene is strong and effectively pins the Fermi energy, making electrostatic gating highly inefficient and the large intrinsic n-type of doping on the order of $\sim 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ difficult to reduce [42]. As a result, the 2010 experiments, which first demonstrated the viability of epitaxial graphene for quantum electrical metrology, could not benefit from the more relaxed operating conditions later achieved for graphene [21]. Instead, these experiments required extreme conditions similar to those used for conventional semiconductors [20]. The realization of the QHR at relaxed magnetic flux densities of $\sim 5 \text{ T}$ and temperatures of $\sim 4 \text{ K}$ (achievable for simpler cryo-cooled instruments) requires reduction and stabilization of carrier density in the low 10^{11} cm^{-2} range while maintaining high mobility and minimal dissipation ($\rho_{xx} \sim 10 \mu\Omega$) [22, 66, 67]. Many different doping methods have been developed to try to overcome this intrinsic drawback [68–71].

Currently, one popular approach uses chemical doping based on 2,3,5,6-tetrafluoro-7,7,8,8-tetracyanoquinodimethane (F4-TCNQ) molecules [71]. The process for charge carrier density control is based on a two-layer resist-system spin-coated onto the graphene Hall bar after microfabrication, consisting of a thin layer of F4-TCNQ/PMMA dopant blend covered by a passive copolymer top-layer [22]. While the F4-TCNQ doping is central for charge-carrier density control, removal of surface adsorbates and contamination after microfabrication as well as additional encapsulation methods such as using thick polymer overlayers, glass elements, or flip-chip encapsulation are critical for long-term stability and AC robustness [67, 72–74]. Polymer-assisted molecular doping and encapsulation methodology provides permanent, homogeneous, and tunable densities with low drift over years and has been validated in interlaboratory comparisons [24].

An alternative method common at NIST applies covalent functionalization of the graphene surface with chromium tricarbonyl $\text{Cr}(\text{CO})_3$, which yields gateless, reversible tuning of the carrier density by annealing in inert atmosphere [66].

These methods are both viable options to reduce the strong n-doping, and controllably bring the carrier density of epitaxial graphene down to desired levels for use in metrology at relaxed operating conditions of temperature and magnetic field [24, 41, 75]. It is even possible to cross the charge neutrality point into p-type doping if desired [72].

2.8. Arrays

The QHE has been used since 1980s in resistance metrology due to the generation of quantized resistance values. However, one limitation is that the values based on a single Hall bar device are quite restrictive. Conventional materials such as GaAs typically provide access to two well-quantized resistance plateaus: $h/(2e^2) \approx 12.9 \text{ k}\Omega$ and $h/(4e^2) \approx 6.45 \text{ k}\Omega$ [26]. For epitaxial graphene, which is now the material of choice, there is in fact only one quantized resistance value which is useful in practice: $h/(2e^2)$. In order to cover the vast range of resistance values in industry, other conventional artifact standards must be employed, thereby increasing the uncertainty at the final calibration step.

Since the advent of QHE, the idea has existed to use series and parallel connections of multiple Hall bars to achieve arbitrary values of resistances [62, 76]. These interconnected devices are called arrays, and they are a deceptively simple concept. Firstly, all individual Hall bars must be well-quantized and with comparable operating conditions (e.g. temperature, magnetic field, and current). This is a question of uniformity and homogeneity, requiring high yield from the fabrication process especially for large arrays consisting of numerous individual elements. Secondly, one must also minimize the influence of undesired resistance from leads and contacts of the interconnects. These constraints have made it historically difficult to produce large graphene quantum Hall array resistance standards (QHARS) with comparable performance to its single-Hall bar counterparts [30, 32, 77, 78].

As described in the Fabrication section above, the reliability and reproducibility of graphene fabrication technology have seen significant developments since it was first used for electrical metrology in 2010. Recent developments saw the use of superconducting leads, combined with multi-terminal connections, to circumvent the issues with the resistance of interconnects [59], enabling a new way of creating graphene QHARS [31, 79]. These developments have led to graphene QHARS with hundreds of connected elements, with a quantization accuracy comparable to single Hall bar devices [33], as shown in figure 7.

For extreme resistance values, QHARS can be made using star-mesh networks which simulate a large resistance values by connecting a limited number of physical Hall bars in special networks [80]. They provide an alternative approach to making arrays with a limited amount of physical components on the chip.

Figure 7. (a) Schematic representing the connection scheme for an exact 100Ω QHARS. Each resistor represents the quantized resistance of one Hall bar. R_1 and R_2 are subarrays consisting of only parallel connections. (b) Optical image of a large QHARS containing ~ 1000 elements. The entire chip is approximately $10 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$.

Graphene QHARS can now cover a wide range of resistance values, from 100Ω to above $1 \text{ G}\Omega$. The existence of these arrays provides access to direct comparison and calibration of conventional standard with quantum standards, decreasing measurement uncertainties by eliminating intermediate steps using artifact standards. The technology behind QHARS is at the present mature enough that they are available commercially.

2.9. Perspective

The various improvements to the fabrication methods, in combination with the refined material growth process, have made epitaxial graphene devices viable for use in metrology and even available commercially. It is perhaps the first, and only, example of a commercially available technology with graphene which truly utilizes the two-dimensional nature of the material.

Single Hall bar devices have been available commercially for over a decade and can be considered a mature technology. Due to their simple design, device yield for single Hall bars can be $>90\%$ when following established fabrication steps.

Graphene arrays have only recently begun to be used more frequently. While comprehensive data on the yield is limited, the increased complexity understandably results in lower yields compared to single devices. Based on RISE's experience, the yield for larger arrays comprising hundreds of Hall bar elements is approximately 50% . Future advancements in material growth, microfabrication, and doping techniques are expected to further enhance device yield and improve the affordability of graphene devices for industrial applications.

3. Stability of epitaxial graphene devices

Graphene-based devices for quantum metrology make resistance calibrations much more practical compared to conventional semiconducting materials. The possibility to observe the QHE at higher temperatures, lower magnetic fields, and using larger bias currents all contributes to the reason that graphene is gradually replacing its historical counterparts around the world. However, one aspect where graphene still has a distinct weakness is its lack of long-term stability. It is no small feat to be able to reproducibly create working graphene devices with fine-tuned performance since graphene is a delicate atomically thin material whose properties can be influenced by exposure to just about anything [81, 82].

Despite careful control over carrier density using various doping methods, the resulting devices can still drift if left exposed to ambient for prolonged periods [83]. These methods do offer some protection to graphene in the form of encapsulation, but prolonged exposure to ambient conditions still induces slow but discernible change in carrier density. Typically, the sample become more p-doped, which is the same behavior seen for pristine graphene [84]. For metrological applications, this is undesirable since the optimal operating condition can change with time as the carrier density drifts. If the drift is significant, the device can lose accurate quantization. One remaining advantage of conventional semiconductors used for quantum resistance standards is their long-term stability under ambient conditions, where they can retain their performance for decades. Here is one aspect where graphene still has room for improvement.

For devices doped using F4-TCNQ molecules, one accessible way to store devices is to use an inert atmosphere such as nitrogen (e.g. nitrogen closet), helium gas, or vacuum (e.g. inside a cryostat) [24]. These inert atmospheres show a significantly reduced rate of carrier density drift compared to ambient exposure. There is a discernible drift, which trends towards higher n-doping, indicating that there is a slow degradation of the molecular dopant (which provide p-doping to counteract the intrinsic n-doping). The electron density drift rate is as small as 0.02% per day. The estimated lifetime of such a device is still on the order of a decade owing to the fact that the operating conditions of graphene quantum Hall state cover a wide range of temperatures, magnetic fields, and currents [21].

A more practical storage solution can be found using a simple sealed glass container, filled with desiccant (e.g. silica gel) [83]. The ubiquity of this storage type makes it convenient for limited times, but it is not suited for year-long storage. The drift tends to be towards p-type, which is the same as for ambient exposure but simply reduced in rate. By combining an oxygen absorber with the desiccant, the resulting storage environment can be extremely stable with the lowest recorded drift of carrier density thus far [83]. The relative change in the carrier density per day is as small as 0.01%. This drift rate is lower compared to when stored under inert atmospheric conditions. Care needs to be taken to use the correct ratio, since the oxygen absorber (based on ferrous oxide) by itself induces extremely strong n-doping.

The various doping methods and storage solutions are relatively new, so it remains to be seen if graphene devices can truly stand the test of time. Thus far, doped graphene samples have shown promise with at least years of recorded stability, with the potential to extend up to decades.

There is ongoing active research to improve both the stability of dopants and storage methods. Recently, mitigation strategies have been investigated which can prolong device lifetime despite drift [23].

4. Graphene-based quantum resistance standards

The metrological performance of epitaxial graphene Hall devices is on par with conventional GaAs devices for the quantum resistance standards. Using cryogenic current comparator (CCC) resistance bridges, the consistency and universality of the QHR in both types of devices were verified at the ppb level [19, 20, 22, 33, 41, 48, 63, 67]. High-quality epitaxial graphene devices sustain substantially larger measurement currents while preserving quantization, which improves signal-to-noise, and are compatible with higher operating currents in the few-100 μA range for single devices and even into the mA range for well-designed arrays [33, 41, 46, 67]. This higher-current capability is instrumental when the QHR is employed directly as a reference in Kibble (Planck) balances, where practical implementations would profit from, for example, 100 Ω QHARSs that can support bias currents on the order of 5–10 mA [33, 63, 85].

A sequence of international interlaboratory comparisons has rigorously validated the equivalence of graphene- and GaAs-based standards. A bilateral comparison between NIST (graphene) and National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology of Japan (AIST) (GaAs) showed agreement for a 100 Ω resistance reference down to ~ 5 $\text{n}\Omega/\Omega$, demonstrating practical stability upon shipment and reinstallation [5]. A tri-lateral study across the Czech Metrology Institute (CMI), KRISS, and PTB with polymer-encapsulated, p-doped graphene devices, transported in an over-pressurized chamber, found reproducibility at $\sim 1 \times 10^{-9}$ under 3.5–7.5 T and 4.2 K, and also assessed AC behavior near 1 kHz using double-shielded devices and digital impedance bridges [66]. Recent bilateral comparison of QHRs in graphene devices between PTB and Bureau International des Poids et Mesures (BIPM) verifies that the metrological Hall quantization is reliably achieved at a magnetic field of 5 T and a temperature of 4.2 K with the degree of equivalence smaller than 2 $\text{n}\Omega/\Omega$ [22]. In May 2025, PTB and the BIPM conducted an on-site comparison under the ongoing program BIPM.EM-K12, where for the first time in this comparison program, both GaAs- and graphene-based QHR devices were successfully used for the realization of the ohm and agreement between the two types of resistance standards was demonstrated within 1 $\text{n}\Omega/\Omega$ [86]. This complements earlier precision universality tests [19], establishing agreement between the QHR in both types of devices and underpins the broader adoption of graphene-based primary resistance standards. Figure 8 depicts the QHE in an epitaxial graphene device [21]. The Hall resistance (red) starts to be quantized at the nominal value of $h/(2e^2)$ at a magnetic field of above 2 T, while the longitudinal resistance (green) is correspondingly suppressed close to zero. The metrology-grade wide Hall resistance quantization can be achieved at a threshold magnetic field of approximately 4 T, in comparison to a narrow counterpart of a GaAs device, as shown in figure 8. The characterization of the QHR plateau (figure 8(e)) shows that the longitudinal resistivity ρ_{xx} of another graphene device

is zero within the uncertainty for $B \geq 5$ T, $T = 4.2$ K and $I \approx 39$ μ A, confirming the integrity of the QHR.

Given this progress, the international community is extending established best practices to explicitly include graphene. A Consultative Committee for Electricity and Magnetism (CCEM) task group, led by NIST, is preparing a user-friendly companion guide that adapts and expands the GaAs-centric technical guidelines for reliable DC QHR measurements to graphene devices, covering specific device and contact properties, quantization parameter spaces, and practical handling⁴. In parallel, guidance for AC QHR metrology with graphene has been consolidated in a good-practice document for realizing the farad with digital impedance bridges and graphene Hall bars, working toward harmonized procedures in both DC and AC regimes as an outcome of the European Partnership on Metrology research program GIQS [64].

The compatibility of graphene-QHR with compact, cryogen-free platforms is a significant practical advantage. Metrological-grade QHR operation has been demonstrated in cryogen-free, table-top systems using pulse-tube coolers and magnets with a maximum field up to 5 T or 7 T, eliminating liquid helium consumption and enabling continuous operation of QHR standard in ordinary laboratory settings [41, 75]. Recent engineering at KRISS with a closed-cycle top-loader cryostat shows that remote-mounting and heavy acoustic isolation of the rotary valve can suppress vibration-induced current noise near 1 Hz and harmonics, supporting reliable graphene-QHR operation and equivalence to the institute's GaAs standard within expanded uncertainties on the order of 7 n Ω / Ω via a 1 k Ω reference resistor [87]. The advantages of cryogen-free systems, such as lower cost of ownership, ease of use, and year-round availability, are balanced by challenges. Especially mechanical vibrations from the cold head and cyclical temperature fluctuations are tackled with proper isolation, cable design, shielding, and thermal engineering [41, 75, 87].

Looking ahead, graphene QHR technology is set to broaden direct access to quantum-accurate resistance standards. As compact systems and robust graphene devices become routine, more NMIs and accredited laboratories can operate primary standards in-house, shortening calibration chains and improving uncertainty budgets for end users [41, 48, 63, 75]. At the same time, graphene-based arrays promise scalable resistance values from 100 Ω to 1 M Ω [33]. The ongoing integration of graphene

⁴ Companion Guide to the Revised Technical Guidelines for Reliable dc Measurements of the Quantized Hall Resistance for Graphene-Based Devices by CCEM Task Group on Graphene QHR Standards (to be published)

Hall devices and acceptance as primary standards in the BIPM key-comparison program (BIPM.EM-K12) and the forthcoming CCEM companion guide should accelerate consistent international adoption [86]. In parallel, the metrology community is working towards the idea of a universal electrical standard with the goal of realizing a single, practical experiment that jointly realizes the volt, ohm, and ampere with quantum accuracy, in which graphene-based QHR can play a central enabling role due to its relaxed operating conditions and compatibility with compact platforms [85]. Altogether, epitaxial graphene brings the QHR standard from specialized cryogenic facilities into compact, reliable instruments, enabling more pervasive, lower-overhead realization and dissemination of the ohm.

5. Impedance quantum standards based on epitaxial graphene devices

In addition to realizing the unit ohm, the QHR operated with AC enables the realization and dissemination of the impedance units farad and henry from a single quantum effect anchored to exact constants h and e . Put simply, a QHR standard operated in the $i = 2$ plateau realizes $R_K/2$ and, when used under strictly coaxial conditions such that all currents contributing to the Hall potential are correctly routed through the device, it can serve as a quantum standard of impedance rather than ‘only’ a DC resistance standard [88, 89]. In practice, two complementary strategies are often used to achieve metrologically clean AC operation. First, double-shielding surrounds the Hall bar with a driven shield that intercepts stray capacitive currents and feeds them back into the measurement loop. This restores ideal bridge conditions and suppresses the frequency-dependence of the Hall plateau, enabling direct realization of the farad from the QHR [88–91]. Second, one may extrapolate the measured Hall value to zero AC dissipation by correlating deviations from $R_K/2$ with the longitudinal resistance R_{xx} [88–90].

Device operation and bridge configuration must follow specific connection schemes. The multiple- (typically triple-) series connection of equal-potential contacts minimizes the influence of lead and contact impedances [62]. Rigorous AC characterization of contact and longitudinal impedances is needed to verify the device integrity for AC QHR operation [92]. In addition to low contact resistances on the level of a few ohm and the vanishing of R_{xx} in the 10 $\mu\Omega$ to 100 $\mu\Omega$ level, the magneto capacitance and the imaginary parts of the longitudinal impedance Z_{xx} (C_x and L_x) are further investigated for the assessment of the device integrity [92–95]. Interlaboratory studies by CMI, KRISS, and PTB on polymer-encapsulated, double-shielded epitaxial-graphene Hall bars have demonstrated DC agreement with $R_K/2$ at the 1 n Ω/Ω level over 3.5–7.5 T and reproducible AC quantization around 1 kHz within 0.1 $\mu\Omega/\Omega$ after international shipment in inert environments and repeated cool-downs. These results indicate that F4-TCNQ-stabilized devices are suitable for AC operation and sufficiently stable in carrier density for practical dissemination [66], but also Cr(CO)₃ has been demonstrated to be compatible [29, 70, 95]. The remaining frequency dependence in AC operation may be attributed to different dissipative effects in the two-dimensional electron system, surface near layers or in other parts of the device. The devices exhibit larger losses for in-plane electric-field components than for perpendicular fields, with dissipation linked to compressible puddles embedded in incompressible regions and to screening at the device edge. Because shielding and device geometry control the field distribution, understanding and engineering screening is central to minimizing the residual frequency dependence of R_{xy} and is an active focus of international work [89, 93–95].

Impedance bridges provide the practical link between the QHR and laboratory standards. Historically, inductive-voltage-divider transformer bridges offered the most accurate 4-terminal impedance ratios. In realization used at the PTB, a 10 nF (or 1 nF) capacitance is calibrated directly against $R_K/2$ at ~ 1233 Hz and then disseminated through 10:1 ratio chains, achieving uncertainties of a few parts in 10^{-9} for the farad. These bridges remain benchmarks for ultimate accuracy but are complex, narrow-band, and largely manual [88]. Fully digital bridges replace the transformer entirely with phase-coherent synthesized sources, providing broadband (≈ 50 Hz–50 kHz) automated 4-terminal measurements and direct comparison of unlike impedances. In their most advanced form, Josephson-based digital bridges use two Josephson arbitrary-waveform synthesizers (JAWS) to generate quantum-accurate, low-distortion sine waves at arbitrary phase, covering general points in the complex plane and shortening the calibration chain [29, 96, 97]. PTB and the Federal Institute of Metrology of Switzerland have implemented four-terminal-pair Josephson impedance bridges that employ two pulse-driven JAWS with fine amplitude/phase control to realize arbitrary ratios and quadrature balances [29, 96, 98]. Leveraging the low Johnson noise of the QHR, these bridges have directly linked graphene-based QHR to 10 nF and decade capacitances near 1.233 kHz with repeatability of a few 10^{-8} , as illustrated in figure 9. A subsequent PTB–Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica (INRIM) comparison between this Josephson bridge and INRIM/Politecnico di Torino (POLITO)’s fully digital bridge confirmed consistent realization

of the farad in the 4-terminal configuration [29, 97]. As a laboratory-friendly alternative, CMI's reconfigurable fully digital bridge uses synchronized high-stability waveform generators and an injection technique to achieve fixed 1:1 R:C linkages at the 10^{-7} level, 10^{-8} for 10:1 scaling, and even a 129:1 comparison of a 100 pF capacitor to 12.9 k Ω at ≈ 1 kHz using QHR standards. These results support shorter traceability chains that still retain strong links to quantum standards [96, 99, 100].

Impedance quantum metrology is advancing through coordinated optimization of devices, packaging, probe design and bridges. On the device side, reproducible and stable carrier-density control, geometry that suppresses in-plane fields, and active near-chip shielding are being refined to further reduce losses and related frequency dependence [66, 73, 93, 101]. On the systems side, Josephson-synthesized digital bridges have removed analog components such as ratio transformers and inductive voltage dividers. Next-generation instruments target lower noise, automated self-calibration and self-tests, and direct QHR to capacitance/inductance linkages across a broader audio bandwidth, extending into the multi-kHz range [29, 97, 98]. In parallel, alternative traceability chains based on fully digital bridges capable of direct 12.9 k Ω : 100 pF comparisons shorten the dissemination and provide independent cross-checks to Josephson-based realizations, strengthening international consistency [96, 99, 100]. Collectively, these advances point to a landscape in which graphene Hall devices, operated in cryogen-free cryostats and coupled to digital bridges, realize the ohm, farad, and henry from the same device with uncertainties in the low 10^{-8} range over a significantly broadened frequency window [29, 66, 93, 96–98].

6. Electrical current metrology with epitaxial graphene devices

Precise realization and measurement of electrical currents, directly traceable to the elementary charge of e and the defining constant of $\Delta\nu_{Cs}$ (the hyperfine transition frequency of cesium) in the SI [102], are challenging in any range. If a scalable invariant resistance is realized with a QHR array, electrical current can be generated or measured in the framework of Ohm's law, as described in the *mise en pratique* [103]. Compared with the QHR in GaAs, a relatively large current can be driven without breaking the quantum Hall state in graphene. For instance, a 0.1 kg mass realization requires a current close to 1 mA in a Kibble balance at NIST [34]. For precision current evaluation in the NIST Kibble balance, the current is driven through a graphene-based QHR array, comprising 13 graphene Hall devices integrated in parallel, and the resultant quantized Hall voltage is evaluated by using the programmable Josephson voltage standard (PJVS). Previously, GaAs-based [104] or graphene-based [34] QHR arrays were employed for an ideal current-to-voltage conversion. However, those require sub-helium temperatures and high magnetic fields close to 10 T. A GaAs QHR array in [104] is operational at a magnetic field of 9.5 T and at a temperature of 0.3 K, and even the graphene QHR array in [34] requires a demanding operational environment ($B = 9$ T and $T = 1.6$ K). In addition, the previous configuration of the array-based current-to-voltage conversion has a large input resistance unlike an ideal ammeter with zero input resistance.

An ammeter can comprise a current-to-voltage preamplifier with a feedback resistor and a voltmeter as illustrated in figure 10(a). Note that the input resistance for a metrological current-to-voltage converter can be reduced to as small as sub-m Ω [105]. Since the physical resistor and the solid-state voltmeter are temporally and environmentally unstable, both artifacts require timely calibrations for

precision current measurements. We can conceive that both are replaced with quantum mechanical components as depicted in figure 10(b). That is, the feedback resistor is replaced with a scalable QHR array, and the voltmeter is substituted with PJVS and a voltage null detector. If the QHR array is made of graphene, the operational environment ($B = 5$ T and $T = 4$ K) can be achieved cost-effectively with a cryocooler. The corresponding quantum mechanical ammeter is indeed under development by a Consortium in the European Partnership on Metrology (23FUN05 AQuanTEC) [106]. The target current and uncertainty are $1 \mu\text{A}$ and $0.1 \mu\text{A A}^{-1}$, respectively. Note that multiple-series connections [107] are implemented between a terminal of an operational amplifier at room temperature and contacts at 4 K to effectively reduce the interconnection resistance of a few Ω with respect to the QHR array, as illustrated in figure 10(b).

We can extend the applications of epitaxial graphene beyond electrical current measurement. Previously, electrical currents were generated with a series connection of PJVS and a $1 \text{ M}\Omega$ GaAs QHR array [108]. This type of passive current source is indeed affected by a connected load resistance, far from an ideal current source. A commercial active current source comprises a resistor, a solid-state voltage source, and an operational amplifier for feedback control. An output current is maintained by adjusting the solid-state voltage bias in the feedback mode even with a resistive load connected to the current source. Nevertheless, those solid-state electronic components are inherently unstable. We can conceive of the replacement of the resistor and the voltage source with graphene QHR (/QHR array) and PJVS, respectively. Especially, the graphene QHR array has a merit for a large current. Note that a new PJVS may need to be developed for a large current (>1 mA) generation because the standard PJVS was developed for a large voltage, not for a large current. Another approach is that the current generated by the series connection of PJVS and QHR (/QHR array) can be scaled with a quantum mechanical transformer, such as CCC [109, 110]. We can also consider integrating graphene-based QHR (array) and PJVS into a single compact 4 K closed-cycle cryomagnet. Since a quality epitaxial graphene achieves a metrological Hall quantization as small as 3 T [21], the magnetic field shielding for PJVS may become simpler than the counterpart [111] in GaAs. The integration of quantum resistance and voltage standards may provide possibilities for the quantum current source or quantum ammeter [85].

7. Conclusions and outlook

In this perspective, we have described recent advances in quantum electrical metrology using epitaxial graphene, whose prominence dates to the isolation of graphene flakes in 2004 and to the Nobel Prize in 2010. The underlying physics of graphene enables the realization of the quantum resistance standard under more easily accessible experimental conditions. As K. von Klitzing emphasized in his presentation at the 26th General Conference on Weights and Measures at the BIPM on 16 November 2018, ‘Metrology focuses on *practical* applications for all time, for all people.’ Over the past decade and a half, community efforts with epitaxial graphene have translated into practical metrological applications spanning resistance, impedance, and current. Unlike GaAs-based quantum resistance standards, which generally require significant liquid-helium consumption, graphene-based realizations in compact closed-cycle cryomagnets broaden access to high-quality measurements. This aligns with the spirit of the SI revision that has been in effect since 20 May 2019.

This perspective focuses on recent progress of epitaxial graphene devices for metrology given the reproducibility of the properties of fabricated devices and its metrological viability proven by

publications in recent years. This focus does not imply that other graphene platforms, such as exfoliated graphene and CVD graphene, lack potential for metrological applications. For instance, an interface-enhanced quantum Hall phase has been recently demonstrated in a hybrid system of graphene-insulator (CrOCl) with dual gates below a magnetic field of 1 T and at a temperature as high as 80 K [112]. If the employed heterostructure, built by a bottom-up approach for scientific purposes, becomes scalable, Hall devices could be made through scalable microfabrication processes for practical metrology.

Looking ahead, cost-effective closed-cycle cryomagnets should enable routine realization of the quantum resistance standard for commercial calibration services beyond NMIs. While further research is still needed, there is no fundamental obstacle to implementing also a graphene-based impedance quantum standard in a closed-cycle cryomagnet, both for primary impedance traceability and for commercial services. Finally, a universal electrical quantum standard that combines a graphene-based quantum resistance standard and a Josephson voltage standard in a single cryostat to provide resistance, voltage and current at DC and AC is within the realms of possibility.

Acknowledgments

Authors thank Stephan Bauer for valuable comments on the manuscript. This work was in part supported by the National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF) Grant funded by the Korea government (Ministry of Science and Information and Communication Technology) (No. RS-2024-00468515). Part of this work has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology (23FUN05 AQuanTEC), co-financed by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

Data availability statement

All data that support the findings of this study are included within the article (and any supplementary files).

Author contributions

Dong-Hun Chae 0000-0001-6394-9182

Conceptualization (lead), Funding acquisition (lead), Project administration (lead), Visualization (equal), Writing – original draft (equal), Writing – review & editing (equal)

Hans He 0000-0003-1962-5572

Conceptualization (supporting), Visualization (equal), Writing – original draft (equal), Writing – review & editing (equal)

Mattias Kruskopf 0000-0003-2846-3157

Conceptualization (supporting), Visualization (equal), Writing – original draft (equal), Writing – review & editing (equal)

References

- [1] Wallace P R 1947 The band theory of graphite *Phys. Rev.* **71** 622–34
- [2] Novoselov K S, Geim A K, Morozov S V, Jiang D, Zhang Y, Dubonos S V, Grigorieva I V and Firsov A A 2004 Electric field in atomically thin carbon films *Science* **306** 666–9
- [3] Knox H W 1990 Femtosecond carrier dynamics in modulation-doped quantum wells *Surf. Sci.* **229** 371–3
- [4] Gan Y, Chu W and Qiao L 2003 STM investigation on interaction between superstructure and grain boundary in graphite *Surf. Sci.* **539** 120–8
- [5] Blakely J M, Kim J S and Potter H C 1970 Segregation of carbon to the (100) surface of nickel *J. Appl. Phys.* **41** 2693–7
- [6] Eizenberg M and Blakely J M 1979 Carbon monolayer phase condensation on Ni(111) *Surf. Sci.* **82** 228–36
- [7] Van Bommel A J J, Crombeen J E and Van Tooren A 1975 LEED and Auger electron observations of the SiC(0001) surface *Surf. Sci.* **48** 463–72
- [8] Nagashima A, Nuka K, Satoh K, Itoh H, Ichinokawa T, Oshima C and Otani S 1993 Electronic structure of monolayer graphite on some transition metal carbide surfaces *Surf. Sci.* **287–288** 609–13
- [9] Novoselov K S, Geim A K, Morozov S V, Jiang D, Katsnelson M I, Grigorieva I V, Dubonos S V and Firsov A A 2005 Two-dimensional gas of massless Dirac fermions in graphene *Nature* **438** 197–200

- [10] Zhang Y, Tan Y W, Stormer H L and Kim P 2005 Experimental observation of the quantum Hall effect and Berry's phase in graphene *Nature* **438** 201–4
- [11] The Nobel Prize (available at: www.nobelprize.org/prizes/physics/2010/summary/)
- [12] Novoselov S K *et al* 2007 Room-temperature quantum hall *Science* **315** 1379
- [13] Mattevi C, Kim H and Chhowalla M 2011 A review of chemical vapour deposition of graphene on copper *J. Mater. Chem.* **21** 3324–34
- [14] Emtsev K V *et al* 2009 Towards wafer-size graphene layers by atmospheric pressure graphitization of silicon carbide *Nat. Mater.* **8** 203–7
- [15] De Heer W A, Berger C, Ruan M, Sprinkle M, Li X, Hu Y, Zhang B, Hankinson J and Conrad E 2011 Large area and structured epitaxial graphene produced by confinement controlled sublimation of silicon carbide *Proc. Natl Acad. Sci. USA* **108** 16900–5
- [16] Klitzing K V, Dorda G and Pepper M 1980 New method for high-accuracy determination of the fine-structure constant based on quantized Hall resistance *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **45** 494–7
- [17] Josephson B D 1962 Possible new effects in superconductive tunneling *Phys. Lett.* **1** 251–3
- [18] Ristein J, Mammadov S and Seyller T 2012 Origin of doping in quasi-free-standing graphene on silicon carbide *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **108** 246104
- [19] Janssen T J B M, Williams J M, Fletcher N E, Goebel R, Tzalenchuk A, Yakimova R, Lara-Avila S, Kubatkin S and Fal'ko V I 2012 Precision comparison of the quantum Hall effect in graphene and gallium arsenide *Metrologia* **49** 294–306
- [20] Tzalenchuk A, Lara-Avila S, Kalaboukhov A, Paolillo S, Syväjärvi M, Yakimova R, Kazakova O, Janssen T J B M, Fal'ko V and Kubatkin S 2010 Towards a quantum resistance standard based on epitaxial graphene *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **5** 186–9
- [21] Ribeiro-Palau R *et al* 2015 Quantum Hall resistance standard in graphene devices under relaxed experimental conditions *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **10** 965–71
- [22] Yin Y *et al* 2025 Graphene quantum Hall resistance standard for realizing the unit of electrical resistance under relaxed experimental conditions *Phys. Rev. Appl.* **23** 1
- [23] Rozhko S, Fletcher N and Giblin P S 2025 Carrier concentration adjustment in graphene QHR devices for metrology applications *J. Appl. Phys.* **138** 134503
- [24] He H *et al* 2019 Polymer-encapsulated molecular doped epigraphene for quantum resistance metrology *Metrologia* **56** 045004
- [25] Pollarolo A, Wendler K, He H, Cedergren K and Brown R 2024 Calibration of room-temperature ratio bridge with graphene quantum Hall array device *CPEM Dig. Conf. Precis. Electromagn. Meas.* pp 1–2
- [26] Delahaye F and Jeckelmann B 2003 Revised technical guidelines for reliable dc measurements of the quantized Hall resistance *Metrologia* **40** 217–23
- [27] Gournay P, Rolland B, Kučera J and Vojáčková L 2017 On-site comparison of quantum Hall Effect resistance standards of the CMI and the BIPM: ongoing key comparison BIPM.EM-K12 *Metrologia* **54** 01014
- [28] Kalmbach C C, Schurr J, Ahlers F J, Müller A, Novikov S, Lebedeva N and Satrapinski A 2014 Towards a graphene-based quantum impedance standard *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **105** 073511
- [29] Bauer S *et al* 2021 A four-terminal-pair Josephson impedance bridge combined with a graphene-quantized Hall resistance *Meas. Sci. Technol.* **32** 065007
- [30] Lartsev A, Lara-Avila S, Danilov A, Kubatkin S, Tzalenchuk A and Yakimova R 2015 A prototype of RK /200 quantum Hall array resistance standard on epitaxial graphene *J. Appl. Phys.* **118** 696–708
- [31] Kruskopf M, Rigosi A F, Panna R A, Marzano M, Patel D, Jin H, Newell D B and Elmquist E R 2019 Next-generation crossover-free quantum Hall arrays with superconducting interconnections *Metrologia* **56** 065002
- [32] Park J, Kim S W and Chae D H 2020 Realization of $5 h/e^2$ with graphene quantum Hall resistance array *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **116** 093102
- [33] He H, Cedergren K, Shetty N, Lara-Avila S, Kubatkin S, Bergsten T and Eklund G 2022 Accurate graphene quantum Hall arrays for the new International System of Units *Nat. Commun.* **13** 1–9
- [34] Seifert C F *et al* 2022 A macroscopic mass from quantum mechanics in an integrated approach *Commun. Phys.* **5** 3–8
- [35] Peplow M 2024 Coming of age *Science* **386** 138–43
- [36] Zhao Y and Lin L 2024 Graphene, beyond lab benches twenty years since its discovery, the journey to reach graphene's true potential is still underway *Science* **386** 144–6
- [37] Virojanadara C, Syväjärvi M, Yakimova R, Johansson L, Zakharov A and Balasubramanian T 2008 Homogeneous large-area graphene layer growth on 6H-SiC(0001) *Phys. Rev. B* **78** 245403
- [38] Bae S *et al* 2010 Roll-to-roll production of 30-inch graphene films for transparent electrodes *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **5** 574–8
- [39] Wang C *et al* 2015 Growth of millimeter-size single crystal graphene on cu foils by circumfluence chemical vapor deposition *Sci. Rep.* **4** 4537
- [40] He H, Shetty N, Bauch T, Kubatkin S, Kaufmann T, Cornils M, Yakimova R and Lara-Avila S 2020 The performance limits of epigraphene Hall sensors doped across the Dirac point *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **116** 223504
- [41] Rigosi A F *et al* 2019 Graphene devices for tabletop and high-current quantized Hall resistance standards *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.* **68** 1870–8
- [42] Kopylov S, Tzalenchuk A, Kubatkin S and Fal'ko V I 2010 Charge transfer between epitaxial graphene and silicon carbide *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **97** 112109
- [43] Alexander-Webber J A *et al* 2016 Giant quantum Hall plateaus generated by charge transfer in epitaxial graphene *Sci. Rep.* **6** 30296
- [44] Kruskopf M *et al* 2016 Comeback of epitaxial graphene for electronics: large-area growth of bilayer-free graphene on SiC *2D Mater.* **3** 041002
- [45] Strupinski W *et al* 2011 Graphene epitaxy by chemical vapor deposition on SiC *Nano Lett.* **11** 1786–91
- [46] Yang Y *et al* 2017 Epitaxial graphene homogeneity and quantum Hall effect in millimeter-scale devices *Carbon* **115** 229–36
- [47] Lafont F *et al* 2015 Quantum hall resistance standards from graphene grown by chemical vapour deposition on silicon carbide *Nat. Commun.* **6** 10
- [48] Kruskopf M and Elmquist R E 2018 Epitaxial graphene for quantum resistance metrology *Metrologia* **55** R27–36
- [49] Ferrari A C and Basko D M 2013 Raman spectroscopy as a versatile tool for studying the properties of graphene *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **8** 235–46
- [50] Ni Z H, Chen W, Fan X F, Kuo J L, Yu T, Wee A T S and Shen Z X 2008 Raman spectroscopy of epitaxial graphene on a SiC substrate *Phys. Rev. B, Condens. Matter Mater. Phys.* **77** 115416

- [51] Yager T et al 2013 Express optical analysis of epitaxial graphene on SiC: impact of morphology on quantum transport *Nano Lett.* **13** 4217–23
- [52] Panchal V et al 2018 Confocal laser scanning microscopy for rapid optical characterization of graphene *Commun. Phys.* **1** 83
- [53] Slizovskiy S and Fal'ko V 2017 Cooling of chiral heat transport in the quantum Hall effect regime of graphene *Phys. Rev. B* **96** 075434
- [54] Chae D H, Kim W-S, Oe T and Kaneko N-H 2018 Direct comparison of 1 M Ω quantized Hall array resistance and quantum Hall resistance standard *Metrologia* **55** 645–53
- [55] Lindvall N, Kalabukhov A and Yurgens A 2012 Cleaning graphene using atomic force microscope *J. Appl. Phys.* **111** 064904
- [56] Léonard F and Talin A A 2011 Electrical contacts to one- and two-dimensional nanomaterials *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **6** 773–83
- [57] Xia F, Perebeinos V, Lin Y, Wu Y and Avouris P 2011 The origins and limits of metal-graphene junction resistance *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **6** 179–84
- [58] Yager T et al 2015 Low contact resistance in epitaxial graphene devices for quantum metrology *AIP Adv.* **5** 87134
- [59] Kruskopf M, Rigosi A F, Panna A R, Patel D K, Jin H, Marzano M, Berilla M, Newell D B and Elmquist R E 2019 Two-terminal and multi-terminal designs for next-generation quantized hall resistance standards: contact material and geometry *IEEE Trans. Electron. Devices* **66** 3973–7
- [60] Wang L et al 2013 One-dimensional electrical contact to *Science* **342** 614–7
- [61] Shetty N et al 2023 Scalable fabrication of edge contacts to 2D materials: implications for quantum resistance metrology and 2D electronics *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.* **6** 6292–8
- [62] Delahaye F 1993 Series and parallel connection of multiterminal quantum Hall-effect devices *J. Appl. Phys.* **73** 7914–20
- [63] Rigosi A F and Elmquist R E 2019 The quantum Hall effect in the era of the new SI *Semicond. Sci. Technol.* **34** 093004
- [64] Callegaro L, Bauer S, Jeanneret B, Kruskopf M, Marzano M, Ortolano M and Overney F 2022 Good practice guide on the graphene-based AC-QHE realization of the farad (arXiv:2205.04915)
- [65] Janssen T J B M, Tzalenchuk A, Yakimova R, Kubatkin S, Lara-Avila S, Kopylov S V and Fal'ko V I 2011 Anomalously strong pinning of the filling factor $\nu=2$ in epitaxial graphene *Phys. Rev. B* **83** 3–6
- [66] Chae H D et al 2022 Investigation of the stability of graphene devices for quantum resistance metrology at direct and alternating current *Meas. Sci. Technol.* **33** 065012
- [67] Chatterjee A et al 2023 Performance and stability assessment of graphene-based quantum hall devices for resistance metrology *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.* **72** 1–6
- [68] Lara-Avila S, Moth-Poulsen K, Yakimova R, Bjørnholm T, Fal'ko V, Tzalenchuk A and Kubatkin S 2011 Non-volatile photochemical gating of an epitaxial graphene/polymer heterostructure *Adv. Mater.* **23** 878–82
- [69] Lartsev A, Yager T, Bergsten T, Tzalenchuk A, Janssen M, Yakimova R, Lara-Avila S and Kubatkin S 2014 Tuning carrier density across Dirac point in epitaxial graphene on SiC by corona discharge *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **105** 063106
- [70] Rigosi A F et al 2018 Gateless and reversible Carrier density tunability in epitaxial graphene devices functionalized with chromium tricarbonyl *Carbon* **142** 468–74
- [71] He H et al 2018 Uniform doping of graphene close to the Dirac point by polymer-assisted assembly of molecular dopants *Nat. Commun.* **9** 3956
- [72] Yin Y, Kruskopf M, Bauer S, Tschirner T, Pierz K, Hohls F, Haug R J and Schumacher H W 2024 Quantum Hall resistance standards based on epitaxial graphene with p-type conductivity *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **125** 064001
- [73] Kruskopf M, Kieler O, Chatterjee A, Bauer S and Lengsfeld J 2024 Flip-chip encapsulation of graphene-based quantum resistors *CPEM Dig Conf. Precis. Electromagn. Meas*
- [74] Yin Y, Chatterjee A, Momeni D, Kruskopf M, Götz M, Wundrack S, Hohls F, Pierz K and Schumacher H W 2022 Tailoring permanent charge carrier densities in epitaxial graphene on SiC by Functionalization with F4-TCNQ *Adv. Phys. Res.* **1** 2200015
- [75] Janssen T J B M, Rozhko S, Antonov I, Tzalenchuk A, Williams J M, Melhem Z, He H, Lara-Avila S, Kubatkin S and Yakimova R 2015 Operation of graphene quantum Hall resistance standard in a cryogen-free table-top system *2D Mater.* **2** 035015
- [76] Ortolano M, Abrate M and Callegaro L 2015 On the synthesis of quantum Hall array resistance standards *Metrologia* **52** 31–39
- [77] Woszczyna M, Friedemann M, Dziomba T, Weimann T and Ahlers F J 2011 Graphene p-n junction arrays as quantum-Hall resistance standards *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **99** 2011–4
- [78] Schopfer F and Poirier W 2007 Testing universality of the quantum Hall effect by means of the Wheatstone bridge *J. Appl. Phys.* **102** 054903
- [79] Panna A R et al 2021 Graphene quantum Hall effect parallel resistance arrays *Phys. Rev. B* **103** 075408
- [80] Jarrett D G et al 2023 Graphene-based star-mesh resistance networks *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.* **72** 1–10
- [81] Wang L, Sofer Z and Pumera M 2020 Will any crap we put into graphene increase its electrocatalytic effect? *ACS Nano* **14** 21–25
- [82] Panchal V, Giusca C E, Lartsev A, Martin N A, Cassidy N, Myers-Ward R L, Gaskill D K and Kazakova O 2016 Atmospheric doping effects in epitaxial graphene: correlation of local and global electrical studies *2D Mater.* **3** 015006
- [83] Shetty N, Bergsten T, Eklund G, Avila S L, Kubatkin S, Cedergren K and He H 2023 Long-term stability of molecular doped epitaxial graphene quantum Hall standards: single elements and large arrays ($R_K/236 \approx 109 \Omega$) *Metrologia* **60** 055009
- [84] Panchal V, Pearce R, Yakimova R, Tzalenchuk A and Kazakova O 2013 Standardization of surface potential measurements of graphene domains *Sci. Rep.* **3** 2597
- [85] Poirier W and Djordjevic S 2025 A universal quantum electrical standard is getting closer *Nat. Electron.* **8** 632–4
- [86] Gournay P et al 2025 On-site comparison of quantum Hall effect resistance standards of the PTB and the BIPM: ongoing key comparison BIPM.EM-K12 *Metrologia* **62** 01010
- [87] Chae D-H, Park J and Shin S S 2025 Closed-cycle top-loader for quantum resistance standard in graphene at KRISS *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.* **74** 1–7
- [88] Schurr J, Ahlers F and Kibble B P 2012 The ac quantum Hall resistance as an electrical impedance standard and its role in the SI *Meas. Sci. Technol.* **23** 124009
- [89] Lüönd F, Kalmbach C-C, Overney F, Schurr J, Jeanneret B, Müller A, Kruskopf M, Pierz K and Ahlers F 2017 AC quantum hall effect in epitaxial graphene *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.* **66** 1459–66
- [90] Delahaye F, Kibble B P and Zarka A 2000 Controlling ac losses in quantum hall effect devices *Metrologia* **37** 659–70
- [91] Kibble B P and Schurr J 2008 A novel double-shielding technique for ac quantum Hall measurement *Metrologia* **45** L25–7
- [92] Schurr J, Ahlers F-J, Hein G, Melcher J, Pierz K, Overney F and Wood B M 2006 AC longitudinal and contact resistance measurements of quantum Hall devices *Metrologia* **43** 163–73
- [93] Schurr J, Kalmbach C-C, Ahlers F J, Hohls F, Kruskopf M, Müller A, Pierz K, Bergsten T and Haug R J 2017 Magnetocapacitance and dissipation factor of epitaxial graphene-based quantum Hall effect devices *Phys. Rev. B* **96** 1–12

- [94] Overney F, Eichenberger A L, Bauer S, Ortolano M, Marzano M, Yin Y and Kruskopf M 2024 Longitudinal impedance measurements on graphene QHE devices *2024 Conf. on Precision Electromagnetic Measurements (CPEM)* (IEEE) pp 1–2
- [95] Kruskopf M *et al* 2021 Graphene quantum hall effect devices for AC and DC electrical metrology *IEEE Trans. Electron Devices* **68** 3672–7
- [96] Overney F, Lüönd F and Jeanneret B 2016 Broadband fully automated digitally assisted coaxial bridge for high accuracy impedance ratio measurements *Metrologia* **53** 918–26
- [97] Marzano M, Pimsut Y, Kruskopf M, Yin Y, Kraus M, D’Elia V, Callegaro L, Ortolano M, Bauer S and Behr R 2022 PTB-INRIM comparison of novel digital impedance bridges with graphene impedance quantum standards *Metrologia* **59** 065001
- [98] Overney F, Flowers-Jacobs N E, Jeanneret B, Rüfenacht A, Fox A E, Underwood J M, Koffman A D and Benz S P 2016 Josephson-based full digital bridge for high-accuracy impedance comparisons *Metrologia* **53** 1045–53
- [99] Kučera J, Svoboda P and Pierz K 2019 AC and DC quantum hall measurements in gaas-based devices at temperatures up to 4.2 K *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.* **68** 2106–12
- [100] Kučera J, Kováč J, Svoboda P and Bártová L 2025 Alternative traceability chains of impedance units with fully digital impedance bridges *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.* **74** 1–6
- [101] Marzano M, Tran N T M, D’Elia V, Serazio D, Enrico E, Ortolano M, Pierz K, Kučera J and Callegaro L 2020 A coaxial cryogenic probe for quantum Hall effect measurements in the AC regime *24th IMEKO TCA Int. Symp. 22nd Int Work. ADC DAC Model. Test* vol 10 pp 233–8
- [102] Stock M, Davis R, de Mirandés E and Milton M J T 2019 Corrigendum: the revision of the SI—the result of three decades of progress in metrology *Metrologia* **56** 022001
- [103] The BIPM (available at: www.bipm.org/documents/20126/41489676/SI-App2-ampere.pdf)
- [104] Chae D-H *et al* 2020 Quantum mechanical current-to-voltage conversion with quantum Hall resistance array *Metrologia* **57** 025004
- [105] Drung D, Krause C, Giblin S P, Djordjevic S, Piquemal F, Séron O, Renguez F, Götz M, Pesel E and Scherer H 2015 Validation of the ultrastable low-noise current amplifier as travelling standard for small direct currents *Metrologia* **52** 756–63
- [106] AQuanTEC (23FUN05) (available at: <https://ptb.de/epm2023/aquantec>)
- [107] Delahaye F 1993 Series and parallel connection of multiterminal quantum Hall-effect devices *J. Appl. Phys.* **73** 7914–20
- [108] Chae D H, Kim M-S, Oe T and Kaneko N-H 2022 Series connection of quantum Hall resistance array and programmable Josephson voltage standard for current generation at one microampere *Metrologia* **59** 065011
- [109] Brun-Picard J, Djordjevic S, Leprat D, Schopfer F and Poirier W 2016 Practical quantum realization of the ampere from the elementary charge *Phys. Rev. X.* **6** 041051
- [110] Djordjevic S, Behr R and Poirier W 2025 A primary quantum current standard based on the Josephson and the quantum Hall effects *Nat. Commun.* **16** 1–12
- [111] Matsumaru D, Oe T, Nakamura S, Maruyama M and Kaneko N H 2024 Operation of Josephson voltage standard with superconducting shield in magnetic-field environment *CPEM Dig. Conference Prec. Electromagn. Meas.* vol 1 pp 9–10
- [112] Wang Y *et al* 2022 Quantum Hall phase in graphene engineered by interfacial charge coupling *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **17** 1272–9